

Library Theory and Research Section

Data curator: who is s/he?

a survey of international and interdisciplinary perspectives

Project Team first meeting 4/4/2015

Draft Minutes

The Research Team met on 4/4/2015 with the following Agenda:

- Activities to be planned
- Sharing responsibilities

The project aims to clarify the role of Data Curator collecting perceptions and definitions about the role and competencies of the data curator at an international and interdisciplinary level.

The objectives are:

- to prepare a taxonomy (a list of terms in hierarchical structure)
- and an ontology, using a formal representation of a set of concepts.

Research Team participating to the virtual meeting

AMT Anna Maria Tammaro <annamaria.tammaro@unipr.it>

TW Terry Weech <weech@illinois.edu> ,

KM Krystina K. Matusiak" <krystyna.matusiak@du.edu> ,

HO Heidi Kristin Olsen <Heidi-Kristin.Olsen@hioa.no> ,

VC Vittore Casarosa ISTI CNR (<http://www.isti.cnr.it>),

AP Ana Pervan has participated as student selected for preparing the literature and documentary review and supporting the survey.

The project team has discussed the conceptual model of data curator (definitions and concepts, geographical context, LAM convergence, research population outside libraries and LIS professionals), the multilingualism and the geographical coverage of the survey, shared responsibilities and the dissemination of results.

Decisions taken:

- To ask an extension until March 2016
- To complete an annotated bibliography in September 2015
- To realize a job position description terminology October 2015
- To do a longitudinal report on data curator concept in LIS school
- To start with English but to extend possibly to other languages
- To limit to LIS careers and research community support inside libraries
- To share responsibilities according to geographical Area and extend to other geographical Area outside USA and EU engaging LTR SC members
- To engage other IFLA interested Units
- To plan a second Skype meeting in October 2015 after preliminary progress
- To collect data from interviews and questionnaire in November 2015
- To analyse and compare data in December and January 2015
- To produce a first report and a taxonomy in February 2016
- To realize the ontology in March 2016
- To share findings in the IFLA LTR Website and investigate the possibility of an ontology software installed by IFLA
- To plan an Open Session in Columbus 2016 involving key respondents as speakers.

GANTT overview

Task	When	Who	Milestone
Literature and documentary review <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annotated Bibliography • Terminology 	September 30th Sharing Bibliography October 15th Second Skype meeting	AP KM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Glossary of terms • Position Description Terminology
Structured interview to data curators themselves and the people who hire data curators	October 15th <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft interview structure • List of data curators and institutions in USA, EU, LA, Asia, Africa November Interviews to be completed	USA: KM, TW, PO EU: HO, AMT, AP ASIA, AFRICA, LA: LTR members to be contacted	Report to compare and contrast the theoretical concepts drawn for content analysis (concepts articulated in the literature) and practitioners' understanding
Questionnaire to be sent to selected LIS	October 15th <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft 	USA: KM, TW, PO EU: HO, AMT, AP	Survey results

institutions	<p>questionnaire</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> List of LIS Schools in USA, EU, LA, Asia, Africa <p>November Questionnaire to be completed</p>	ASIA, AFRICA, LA: LTR members to be contacted	
Analysis of data	December- January	ALL	Taxonomy
Ontology definition terms, properties and relationships	February	VC, AP	Ontology
Formal description SKOS	March	VC, AP, IT student	Website